

Supplementary

Here we show that connecting ZTG by a higher number of even C atoms, e.g. 4C preserves the planer structure of the system. This confirms that the reason for the twisting in the case of 2ZTG-3C is the weaker bonds in the 3C chain not the longer link size compared to 2ZTG-2C. It is also shown in Fig. S1 (g) that a substrate can help solve the twisting problem in the case of odd C-atoms connecting ZTG nanodots.

Fig. S1. (a) The optimized structure of 2ZTG connected with 4C atoms. (b-e) the corresponding HOMO and LUMO for spin-up and spin-down orbitals. (f) The spin density. (g) The optimized structure of 2ZTG-3C situated above the hBN layer, its HOMO, and LUMO are shown in (h-k), and the spin density is in (l).

Fig. S2. The infrared spectra of zigzag-triangular graphene (ZTG) nanodots laterally connected with two and three C atoms.